

EDUCATION AND INDIGENOUS KNOWLEDGE AMONG THE YORUBA: A NEED FOR RE-EVALUATION

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Abstract

This paper explores the intersection of formal education and indigenous knowledge among the Yoruba and the African community at large, emphasizing the importance of re-evaluating the interplay between Western formal education and traditional African systems of learning. Education, encompassing both formal and informal systems, is essential for holistic human development. However, the dominance of Eurocentric educational paradigms in Africa has led to the marginalization of indigenous knowledge systems, which are rich in cultural values, ethical principles, and practical skills crucial for community development. The study highlights the erosion of Yoruba indigenous knowledge due to modernization, colonization, and migration, stressing the urgent need for preservation and transmission of this knowledge across generations. It underscores the merits and demerits of Western education, noting its contributions to knowledge access, economic progress, and global connectivity, but also its role in cultural erosion and intellectual colonization. Conversely, Yoruba indigenous knowledge fosters moral development, community cohesion, and cultural preservation. Proverbs, idioms, and metaphors in Yoruba culture serve as educational tools for imparting wisdom and societal values. The paper advocates for the integration of indigenous knowledge into formal education systems, positing that this approach can enhance educational relevance, promote cultural sustainability, and support the development of well-rounded individuals capable of addressing local and global challenges.

Keywords:

Yoruba. Education. Indigenous knowledge. Formal education. Informal education. Cultural preservation. Values education. Western education. Integration.

Introduction

Education is an essential part in the process of human development. Education is not just about going to school. It is more than schooling. Schooling is only a part of the education process. Whereas education deals with the total process of human learning by which knowledge is imparted, faculties are trained and different skills are developed. It can also be referred as a process of educating or applying discipline on the mind. In other words, it is a process of character training.

It is the aggregate of all the processes by which a child or young adult develop abilities, attitudes and other forms of behavior, which are of positive value to the society in which he lives. Hence, it can be formal or informal and the success of education lies in harnessing the latent potentials of an individual.

What education is meant to achieve is to enable an all-round development of human. It is to develop the physical, mental, emotional, social, moral and spiritual aspects of life. Education is a life-long process, it starts from the cradle to grave. it is not merely the collection of some information; it is an acquisition of experiences through life in the social and natural environment. The day a person dies is the day the person stops learning. Thus, it can be said that life is education and education is life. According to Alan Rogers, (2014:35), in defining education, he says:

Learning is like breathing – we do it all the time, indeed we cannot live without breathing. But most of the time, we breathe unconsciously, only becoming conscious of it when it goes wrong or when we wish to enhance it for purposes such as sports or singing. Learning, like breathing (and indeed ingesting), is a natural process of engaging with our ever-changing environment and taking from it what we need in order to function and to grow; it is an essential element for living.

Education is being regarded therefore as a veritable tool for inculcating in the individual the skills, abilities, aptitudes, attitudes, interest, values and skills which are necessary for functioning effectively in the society. Education can be given at home, in school, church or mosque, community village or town. Only the literacy aspect of education is best given at school, which is called formal. Meaning that homes provide Home Knowledge; church or mosque provides Religious Knowledge; community provides civil knowledge; etc., which is informal.

Formal and Informal

Formal education is one of the types of education that we have. It refers to the systematic studies organized by the educational system, which begins in elementary school and continues through secondary school, and higher institutions. It is delivered in a highly professional environment on school grounds by well-trained and experienced teachers. Formal education is institutionalized, intentional and planned and provided by public organizations and recognized private bodies.

Formal learning often results in certification and recognition in ratified diplomas or qualifications. The motivation for formal learning tends to link with the pursuit of external rewards, such as assessment grades, more than for other less formal learning types. Some argue that formal learning has more emphasis on cognitive achievement, i.e., successes attributable to cognitive abilities, than other less formal types of learning. Formal learning may be seen as intentional not only on the part of the learner but also on the part of the provider of the learning program. It is consciously and deliberately planned for the modification of behavior with a particular end in view. Thus, both the pupil and the teacher deliberately engage themselves in the process of education with predetermined objective in view.

Informal education is the kind of learning that results from daily life activities related to work, family or leisure. It is not structured (in terms of learning objectives, learning time or learning support) and typically does not lead to certification. Sometimes this type of learning may be

intentional but, in most cases, it is non-intentional. Informal education or learning, unlike formal learning which are spasmodic, situated in specific places and times, is ubiquitous, universal and continuous. Informal education is part of the practices of living. Which means, any place where people act and interact has a learning culture, where learning of some type takes place. Thus, such type of learning does not need preparation or readiness before it takes place. It might sometimes appear to be an involuntary experience. And it is experience that continues without ending until one die.

Sometimes informal education is referred to as traditional educational system. It has no specific trainer/instructor. Supervision is not required; most of the learning is unconscious and involuntary. It most time help in building moral and value in the individual, and make the individual more acquainted with his culture. Informal education evolved as early as creation. It spans through learning how to cook, greet, farm, operate engine, act, etc. it can also take place through sport, media, newspaper, societal involvement, family, religion, among peers, traveling, life experiences, etc.

Western Education

As societies become more complex, and especially when writing is adopted or invented, it becomes necessary for some specialist teachers to be employed, often in institutions called schools or universities. It is at this point, that ideas about education begin to be developed and discussed. Prior to this, the upbringing of children would have been regarded as commonsense and taken for granted. Okpilike Felix, (2012:30), described Western education as being “associated with formal education which is a systematic and planned procedure for transmitting content to achieve state goals.”

The traditional definition of education as the delivery of knowledge, skills and information from teachers to students, is believe to be the standard for Western education. Learning to read and write is key to education as conceived in the West. Western education stresses active learning on their learners and encourages rational thinking.

African Indigenous Knowledge

Indigenous Knowledge is the knowledge exhibited by indigenous people. It is, according to some scholars, the Knowledge used by local people to live in a particular environment; which refer to knowledge and knowledge systems unique to a given culture. Thus, it is what indigenous people know and do, and what they have known and done for generations, practices that evolved through trial and error and proved flexible enough to cope with change.

Education existed in Africa long before the continent was colonized or even before the slave trade. Knowledge, skills and attitudes were passed from generation to generation mostly through word of mouth in the African societies. Indigenous education was not only concerned with the systematic socialization of the young generation into norms, beliefs and collective opinions of the wider society, but also placed a very strong emphasis on learning practical skills and the acquisition of knowledge which was useful to the individual and society as a whole. In broad terms, it emphasized social responsibility, job orientation, political participation and spiritual and moral values.

Some scholars, like Nkondo, argues that the western perception of African indigenous knowledge as mere repetition of practices without any theory to explain them is a depiction of western cultural and intellectual arrogance. The Africans community perspective of African Indigenous knowledge is seen to be an enabling cultural process of cultural, that is, contextually and historically grounded amongst local peoples, rural and urban, certificated and uncertificated, for their own livelihood and advancement. The community perspective encourages the notion of dynamism, and this acknowledges the nature of knowledge, namely, evolving and that it is socially constructed by people to address livelihood needs and challenges.

Yoruba and indigenous Knowledge

The Yorúbás are people whose major homeland is Southwestern Nigeria as one of the major ethnic groups in Africa. They have a history of highly sophisticated sociocultural and political systems. Like other ethnic groups in Africa, the Yorúbás have an impressive system of indigenous Knowledge. They engage in an informal mode of Education. Asimi Alarape, et al. (2021:521), have this to say concerning the indigenous knowledge of the Yoruba people:

Just like other indigenous communities in the world, Yorúbás are experiencing an erosion of Indigenous Knowledge as a result of slavery, mass migration to more developed countries, the influence of westernization, religion interferences, colonization, the First and Second World War, and modernization within the communities. The Yoruba older generations that have direct contact with the Indigenous Knowledge have almost gone and the remnants are already reaching retirement age while the younger Yoruba generations are being influenced by the pressures of modernization. Indigenous knowledge is often marginalized by society, therefore there is an urgent need to share, transfer and distribute this indigenous knowledge from older to younger generations so that its culture and traditions survive and prosper.

There are good values in Yorùbá education. Yorùbá education addresses the needs of the community; it is flexible, and inclusive. It accommodates diverse interests and needs by teaching *Ọmọ́lúwàbí* values (Good moral values) in an inclusive way. Yorùbá education inducted members of society into its mores, customs, principles and practices. It respected individuality and diversity, and so there were no failures or dropouts. The subject matter was vast, with an all-encompassing curriculum. It was complex and based on the *Ọmọ́lúwàbí* ethos, which is education geared towards producing a complete person; a person with a good character, gainfully employed and productively engaged in society.

Yoruba indigenous education teaches children to imbibe these ethical values: Knowledge of language, Belief in God/Spirituality, Respect for God's creations, Respect for nature, Respect for elders, Respect for others, Love for children, Hard work, Spirit of sharing, Spirit of co-operation, Knowledge of family lineage, Avoidance of crime, Avoidance of conflict, Knowledge of family roles, Love of humor, Success through hard work, Skills in hunting and farming, Skills in domestic work, Responsibility to the largest community, Defense of father land.

The mode of teaching in the traditional system of education was not direct as there were no obvious classrooms but teaching was indirectly done in the form of observation, imitation, practice and mimicking. Adage and proverbs were extensively used, as the use of proverbs was to bring out the clear meaning of hidden points in any conversation or argument.

Education and values

Values are internalized social representations or moral beliefs that people appeal to as the ultimate rationale for their actions. Base on Psychological perspective, values are internalized cognitive structures that guide choices by evoking a sense of basic principles of right and wrong (e.g., moral values), a sense of priorities (e.g., personal achievement vs group good), and create a willingness to make meaning and see patterns (e.g., trust vs distrust). Societies, cultures, and other social groups have value-based norms, priorities, and guidelines, which describe what people ought to do if they are to do the ‘right,’ ‘moral,’ ‘valued’ thing.

Values are supposed to influence behavior. In spite of the strong belief that values predict behavior, the effect of values on behavior is subject to situational constraints and affordances. That is, if mobilized or made salient, individual values are linked with behavior and choices but not necessarily otherwise. This value enables moral development, which brings along moral maturity.

An individual with moral maturity is expected to be a responsible, fair, reliable, highly empathetic, self-controlling, people-sensitive, respectful, and law-abiding citizen. These morally mature individuals have integrated moral values into their conscience and internalized it; they do not think of acting against moral values, even when they are alone. These individuals, who are capable of internalizing moral values, believe that violating morality is as dangerous as losing the human dignity.

It is widely believed that moral maturation can be solely possible by handing down the moral values to next generations through education. The values education, which harbors the moral values in itself, is of paramount importance in order to hand down the moral values to next generations by means of education.

Such integration and transmission of Value from generation to generation is literarily part of what African indigenous knowledge is to achieve. African indigenous knowledge is interested in building a morally matured individuals and citizens, who allows values to influence their behaviors and practices.

Value education can take place in different forms, but the main aim of providing it to students in their educational institutions is to make them understand the importance of good values; use and reflect them in their behavior and attitudes; and finally contribute to the society through their good social responsibility and ethics.

The need for value education for character formation in the school setting becomes more apparent with the passing of each day. Even though many agrees to the importance of ethics and good moral value, implementing it and still be successful is what they struggled with. Value education is the intentional effort to develop in young people core ethical and performance values that are widely affirmed across all cultures. To be effective, value education must include all stakeholders in a school community and must permeate school climate and curriculum.

Yoruba/African Indigenous Knowledge: Proverbs, Adage, Idioms, Metaphors, etc.

Proverbs, adages, idioms, metaphors, etc., are some educational curricula by which the African people pass across knowledge and educational values. They serve as educational tools that convey wisdom, values, and cultural heritage from one generation to another. They encapsulate complex ideas and morals in concise and memorable ways, making them effective vehicles for teaching and learning. These linguistic devices often draw from everyday experiences, nature, and social interactions, reflecting the communal nature of African societies and emphasizing the importance of community, respect, hard work, and perseverance. By mastering these linguistic elements, individuals not only gain linguistic proficiency but also acquire a deeper understanding of their culture and heritage.

Following are some common proverbs/adages and their meanings:

1. **“One does not sip hot soup in a hurry.”** This means that, in life, nothing should be done in a haste. This proverb extols the virtues of patience in mankind. It also extols the virtue of rationality among individuals. It is an appeal to a man or a woman to exercise perseverance in his/her attempt to make a life time decision. It is always good to be cautious.
2. **“All lizards lie prostrate no one knows which of them suffers a bellyache.”** This proverb tries to show that sometimes it may be difficult to establish a causal connection between physical characteristics of an individual and his psychological dispositions. It appeals to caution in decision making as physical appearance sometimes leads to deception. It indicates that not all that glitter is gold. It also cautions on minding one’s business. It is warning against prejudice.
3. **“A child may choose to become a leper provided he/she can live an isolated life in the forest”.** This proverb addresses the consequences of an action by recalcitrant young adults who despise elders’ advice. Individuals have no personal identity outside the corporate identity held in custody by the entire society. It is the community that makes man. If one considers themselves to be old enough to take decisions on matters of life, seek to do things their own way then they should be ready to bear the consequences of their actions. It is always good to listen to advice.
4. **“If you throw a stone to the market place you may hit your own household.”** This proverb means that one who is ill-mannered, may not be affected alone, but might end up affecting the community at large. It performs some cautionary roles: by warning individuals of the consequences of wrongdoing, and by deterring them from engaging in social vices. The moral values embodied in this proverb are expected to moderate the individuals’ conduct and behavior. Thus, this proverb is expected to provide the virtue of patience.
5. **“The cobra that blocks the path is going his own way, yet people run away when they see him.”** This proverb indicates that once you get a bad reputation, nobody will trust you even when you intend no harm. One significance of this proverb is to always try to be honest with others. Try as much as possible not to break trust, as that might damage your reputation whether as an individual or as a corporate entity. Also, we should never give others the opportunity to think negatively about us. Lastly, sometimes reputation within some scenarios does not always reflect people's actual behavior. So, we should not be fast to judge issues or others.

6. **“The length of a frog is known only after its death.”** This means that a person’s worth is not appreciated in his lifetime. The proverb teaches us to project ourselves and do our best in our life time. Be willing to accept and embrace what comes, believing that it is for your own and the collective highest good after you are no more. The proverb also teaches that in any given situation or experience, you have the choice to see through the eyes of fear or love, and to do your best no matter the criticisms. It also teaches that we should be cautious in life; because some won’t appreciate you, no matter what you do for them.
7. **“One should not bear one’s stomach a grudge.”** This proverb is said of someone who, however unpleasant, is essential to you; since you have no choice you must put up with him. It teaches the relevance of social relationships as this gives humans emotional support and encouragement in difficult times. Relating with others also gives happiness. It helps us to understand that we need to be courageous and patience with people around us. It also teaches the relevance of family ties.
8. **“When a child goes to the bush, he should look for snails and not for the tortoise.”** It takes much experience to find a tortoise in the bush, but snails are common and any child can find them. Only do what is within your power or you may achieve nothing. The proverb teaches us to cut our coats according to our sizes. Meaning that we should not expect too much in life. Again, the proverb is relevant because it helps us to measure our lives as humans in whatever we do. It teaches that we should never be greedy in life. Also, another relevance of the proverb focuses on appreciation. We should learn to appreciate whatever little we have.
9. **“A bird’s relative is the one with whom it shares a nest.”** Common problems bring together those that are affected by them. This means that, your issues, no matter what the root cause, can be alleviated by relating it to people. You cannot expect yourself to do every single goal you set without a plan. Whether it is a friendship, a family relationship, or something else, the breakdown of a relationship is never easy. Good neighborliness is always important.
10. **“If the fish comes out of the water to say that the crocodile is ill, no one should doubt it.”** Nobody will doubt what a close friend says about you. The opinions of your friends are often more important than those of other people, even your family members. Another significance of the proverb is that, it is in your interest to choose your friends wisely. They can be the reason why you succeed or fail in achieving your life goals.
11. **“Knowledge is like a garden: If it is not cultivated, it cannot be harvested.”** If you don’t make efforts to acquire knowledge then you would not expect to have it and if you do not put the knowledge you have to use, you cannot expect to gain anything from it.

There are also some idiomatic/metaphoric expressions that the Yoruba people use in communicating with one another. Examples are:

1. Ta teru nipa (Kick the bucket) – it expresses the fact that someone has died.
2. Fori ja ile agbon – it expresses the fact that someone is in trouble.
3. Eja n bakan? – it is an interrogative statement to find out whether the matter is positive or negative.

4. Akara tu s'epo – it is to express that what is covered as a secret has been revealed
5. Si'so loju eegun – it calls one to say the truth.
6. Fi owo mewewa jeun – it means to spend without saving. Calling for need to curb frugal spending and to inculcate saving mindset.

Comparison Between Formal Education and Indigenous Knowledge (Informal Education)

1. Formal education is classroom-based. While informal education is real life-based, borne out of life experiences.
2. A well-structured environment of learning is provided for formal education. While learning in an informal setting occurs in real-world situations. It might occur in the family, in the neighborhood, through a hobby, or through life experiences.
3. Formal education employs trained teachers or educators to achieve its goal. Informal learning instead is being guided by life experience, which may involve humans or non-humans' tool.
4. While there is a pre-defined goal in formal education, in informal education instead, there is no defined goal because it usually happens spontaneously and naturally.
5. Formal education adheres to an established curriculum. While in informal education, there is no established curriculum
6. Certification is involved in a formal education, the certificate which help in securing space in the work space. Informal education on its own may not require certification, but instead, it grants them learning that will make them valuable in the work place.
7. Formal education is marked by time constraints such as terms, semesters and sessions which are involved in the academic years. While in informal learning there is no time constraints- it begins from birth and ends at death.

Despite the contrast discuss above, the following are some marked similarities between formal education and informal education:

1. Both in formal and informal education social relation and interaction is being developed.
2. Formal education and informal education both have the input of teachers and facilitators- but while formal education is controlled and delivered by educators, informal education happens naturally.
3. Learning is a lifelong process. While formal education occurs at specific times – such as at school, university, and at work – both formal and informal education can happen at any time throughout our lives. Informal learning is spontaneous and continuous, but formal learning can also happen at any point. As soon as you choose to watch an educational video series, enroll in an online course, or take part in a training session, you're taking part in a form of formal learning.

Merit and Demerit of Formal (Western) Education in Africa

Merits:

- 1. Access to Knowledge:** Western education has furnished individuals with the opportunity to explore and acquire a broad range of information across numerous disciplines. This encompasses various fields such as scientific studies, technological advancements, literary works, and creative expressions.
- 2. Economic Development:** The provision of education within the Western framework has played a pivotal role in fostering economic progress and development by imparting essential abilities, competencies and skills required for success in contemporary commercial enterprises and professional sectors.
- 3. Social Mobility:** The availability of education within the Western model has facilitated pathways and social mobility for individuals to transcend their existing socio-economic conditions, enabling them to pursue career prospects that extend beyond conventional vocations.
- 4. Healthcare Improvement:** Acquiring knowledge through education, particularly within the Western framework, frequently demonstrates a positive association with enhanced healthcare results due to the increased cognizance it fosters regarding various health concerns and its encouragement of healthy practices.
- 5. Global Connectivity:** Exposure to Western education promotes a sense of global interconnectedness and connectivity, allowing Africans to actively engage in transnational dialogues, commerce, and diplomatic affairs.

Demerits:

- 1. Cultural Erosion:** While Western education brings numerous benefits, it may inadvertently contribute to the diminishment of indigenous cultures as its ideals and practices occasionally overshadow the rich heritage, rituals, and traditions unique to local communities.
- 2. Dependency:** The reliance on Western educational paradigms and structures can inadvertently cultivate a dependency on these models, potentially resulting in the marginalization of indigenous epistemologies and problem-solving approaches.
- 3. Language Barrier:** A significant proportion of Western educational institutions in Africa employ European languages, such as English or French, as the primary medium of instruction. Example of this is the Yorubas with primary language in English. This linguistic preference can pose significant challenges for students whose native tongue differs from the language used in the classroom. It can also discourage students from embracing and cultivating their native languages and cultural identities.
- 4. Economic Disparities:** While Western education holds the promise of stimulating economic growth, it can also serve to widen existing socio-economic inequalities, given that access to high-quality educational opportunities frequently hinges on one's financial status and privilege.
- 5. Intellectual Colonization:** The predominance of Western educational systems in Africa carries the potential consequence of intellectual colonization, a process through which

African worldviews, epistemologies, and knowledge systems are undermined or stifled in favor of Western ideologies and perspectives.

Need for Promoting African Indigenous Knowledge

It can be noticed that the mode of education in African, even in Yoruba land is Eurocentric in nature. It tends to follow the European culture in all aspect of its educational concept. social theory is still entrenched in the methods, concerns, beliefs and experiences of Western Europe and North America.

Eurocentric discourse has greatly influenced research, teaching and learning of social sciences in higher education in Africa: the principal focus of developments in social thought continues to originate from the work of American, British, French and German scholars. The implication of this is that higher educational institutions in Africa have reduced themselves to the reproduction of the intellectual outputs of social thinkers of western countries, including their theories and methodologies of selection of research problem priorities. As a result of this, there is little attention given to African indigenous literary and philosophical traditions because they tend to be viewed as primitive and unscientific and hence not proper sources for social theory and research development. This is accompanied by the inability of African social scientists to generate their own indigenous concepts, definitions, theories and methods which could guide the intellectual development in their research and academic fields.

African indigenous knowledge should not only be seen as an “alternative” knowledge but as one domain of knowledge among others. Eurocentrism has distorted the real meaning of the concept of “education”. It created and propagated the belief that ‘education’ means western formal systems of schooling introduced to Africa by colonialism, and further developed by post-independence African governments. But when we look at the true meaning of education from its original source in Latin- *educare* and *educere*, it is clear that “education” according to this original conceptualization incorporates all the processes of raising young people to adulthood, and drawing out or developing their potential to contribute to society, which is true with African Indigenous Knowledge.

Thus, as good as formal (Western) education is, the informal (African Indigenous Knowledge) education should not be underrated and discouraged. It is when we allow both to function in our educational system that the total development of a man can be made possible.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Benefits of Integrating African Indigenous Knowledge into the Education System of Africa

One way of increasing the relevance of education is through an environmentally related curriculum based on community needs and conditions. Indigenous knowledge can play an important role in bringing local relevance to education process by bridging the gap between formal education systems and the lived experience within local community contexts. by including indigenous knowledge in the science classroom, the social identities of learners can be acknowledged, learning might be turned into a positive experience and the attitude of learners towards science might change. In whatever form the Indigenous Knowledge may exist, it has the potential of impacting on the teaching-learning situation in significant ways and since this knowledge arises directly out of the children’s real-life experiences, its incorporation into school-

work can serve to motivate students as they begin to see that recognition is given to what they do and say in their communities.

The inclusion of Indigenous Knowledge in education has been seen as one of the tools that can be used to achieve social justice and sustainable development. Preservation of knowledge is also one of the benefits that can be derived from the incorporation of Africa Indigenous Knowledge into the school curriculum.

Integration of African Indigenous Knowledge has pedagogical benefits for students since it enhances educational relevance through a content that speaks of their world view. Integration of Indigenous Knowledge in Higher Education curriculum is crucial for production of human capital that is relevant to provide solutions for the development challenges of a community or country.

The expression of Indigenous Knowledge in a formal educational context provides an opportunity for an inclusive educational approach. While formal (western) education builds in one the skill needed to gain employment in an industry or work environment, informal (Indigenous) education helps build in one the skills and values needed to retain and sustain one's work life in the industry or work environment. Therefore, integrating the two forms of education allows for a whole person development.

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